

Spectrophotometric and Potentiometric Studies on the Composition and Stability of Chromium Propionate Complex

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Spectrophotometric and conductometric methods show the existence of 1:1 complex for the product obtained by refluxing chromic chloride and propionic acid at 70° for 2½ hours. Bjerrum's method has been applied to determine the values of $\log K$ and ΔF of the complex, the values being $^{\circ}74$ and -3.797 kcal. respectively.

The physico-chemical investigations regarding the interaction of Cr(III) with organic acids¹⁻³ are of great importance since these complexes have recently found wide applications in industry as coating materials⁴. Moreover, the complexity of the process of irreversible fixation of cationic chromium complexes through the carboxyl groups of collagen⁵ in chrome-tanning further demands, for its proper interpretation, the undertaking of such studies.

Except the preliminary studies of Weinland⁶, who obtained a green complex from CrO₃ and propionic acid and a violet complex from sodium propionate and chromic chloride, no systematic study has been described in the existing literature regarding the combination of chromium with propionic acid.

The present communication describes the detailed study of the interaction of chromium(III) with propionic acid, using spectrophotometric (modified molar-ratio⁷ and Job's method^{8,9} of continued variation) and potentiometric methods (Bjerrum's method¹⁰).

EXPERIMENTAL

A.R. samples of Cr(III) chloride and sulphate were used for preparing the solutions and their concentrations determined colorimetrically¹¹. Propionic acid and potassium chloride were also of A. R. grade. Triple-distilled water was employed to prepare the solutions. ~~Walpole~~ acetate buffers¹² were made from 0.2M solutions and their pH's tested by a Beckman pH meter, Model G.

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Optical density measurements were carried out at 580m μ by means of a Beckman DU spectrophotometer, using tungsten lamp as the light source and 1 cm corex cell. Lambert-Beer's law was found to hold good throughout the whole range of chromium concentration. The reaction between Cr(III) and propionic acid, being a slow one at room temperature, was therefore investigated at higher temperatures. Preliminary experiments were performed after heating the reaction mixture between 60° and 70° for some time.

FIG. 1. Effect of ionic strength on Cr-propionate complex at pH 5.5. The broken lines for $10 \times 10^{-3} \text{Cr}^{3+}$ and full lines for $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{Cr}^{3+}$.

FIG. 2. Effect of pH on the spectra of the complex. Cr^{3+} conc. for curves a and b is $10 \times 10^{-3} M$ and $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ for curve c which represents spectra without buffer.

An aliquot of the mixture (10 ml) was pipetted after short intervals, cooled to room temperature (30°), and optical density measured at different wave lengths to determine the absorption maxima. Although the O. D. values increased with lapse of time, the absorption maxima were found to exist at 580 m μ . When the mixture had been refluxed for 2½ hours, a constancy in the O. D. values could be realised. This condition was then taken for the attainment of equilibrium. Subsequent measure-

ments (optical density, pH , and conductance) were carried out after cooling to room temperature the reaction product obtained on refluxing the reaction mixtures at 70° for 2½ hours.

Solutions of chromic chloride (5 and 10 mM) were taken with propionic acid in the ratio (chromic chloride: propionic acid) 1:0, 1:1, 1:2, 1:3, 1:4, and 1:5 at three different ionic strengths (adjusted to 0.15, 0.3, and 0.60 by addition of KCl). The pH 's were maintained at 4.7 and 5.5 by adding requisite amounts of buffers. Observations were carried out with and without addition of buffers. The results are shown in Figs. 1 and 2 (curves *a*, *b*, and *c*). Experiments under similar conditions were performed using Job's method⁶. The differences between the optical densities of the mixtures and those of the metal ions have been plotted against the varying concentration of chromium ion (Fig. 3, curves *a* and *b*).

Conductometric measurements under identical conditions were carried out by a Cambridge conductivity bridge, type L, 350140, using a Cambridge conductivity cell. The difference in conductance of the mixture and that of the metal ion has been plotted against the increasing concentration of Cr(III) (Fig. 4). No detectable change in the results was observed by either of the above two methods when chromic chloride was replaced by chromic sulphate.

FIG. 3. Curve *c* represents the reaction mixture alone ($pH < 3$).

FIG. 4.

pH Titration (Bjerrum's Method).—To the mixture (10 ml), containing the reactants approximately in the ratio 1:1, A. R. potassium chloride was added to adjust the ionic strength to 0.15. It was then refluxed for 2½ hours, cooled to 30° , and titrated with carbonate-free¹³ potassium hydroxide (pure nitrogen was employed for inert atmosphere

13. Kolthoff and Sandell, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd ed., The Macmillan Co., N. Y., 1952.

as well as for stirring). Column 6 of Table I records the value of log K at $\mu=0.15$ for the complex obtained at 70° .

Stability constant K at $\mu=0.15$ for the reaction:

was calculated with the help of the expression:

$$K = \frac{\bar{n}}{(1-\bar{n})(C_2H_3COO^-)} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

when $\bar{n}$, the average number of propionic acid molecule bound by one chromium atom, is given by

$$\bar{n} = \frac{C_A - [C_2H_3COO^-]}{\text{Total concentration of Cr(III)}} \left[\frac{1 + (H^+)}{K_a} \right]$$

where C_A is the total concentration of propionic acid

(H^+) is known at a particular pH ; the value of K_a is taken from the literature¹⁴ The concentration of free complex-forming species ($C_2H_3COO^-$) was evaluated with the help of the equation:

$$\log (C_2H_3COO^-) = (pH - pK_a + \log [C_A - (KOH)])$$

Thus knowing the values of ($C_2H_3COO^-$) at various pH 's during titration, the value of $\bar{n}$, and hence the stability constant K , was calculated.

TABLE I
Potentiometric titrations.
Ionic strength=0.15. Temp.=30°.

[KOH].	pH.	[C ₂ H ₃ COO ⁻] ×10 ⁴ .	Log [C ₂ H ₃ COO ⁻].	$\bar{n}$.	Log K.
0.00	2.88	..	..	..	..
10.05	3.22	2.01	4.3012	0.10	2.740
19.76	3.62	4.54	4.6571	0.20	2.740
31.75	9.02	9.64	4.9841	0.35	2.746
44.67	4.38	17.90	3.2529	0.50	2.741
63.02	4.92	41.50	3.6180	0.70	2.750
66.49	5.07	53.10	3.7251	0.75	2.750
71.95	5.27	70.40	3.8476	0.80	2.750

Mean 2.740

DISCUSSION

Job's method of continued variation provided a 1:1 complex for the chromic chloride-propionic acid reaction. The composition was not found to be influenced by the change in

14. See Ref. No. 4,

15. Everett *et al.*, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1952, A215, 403.

pH (Fig. 3). The only influence of pH worth mentioning is that the absorbance is higher at pH 5.5 than at pH 4.7. From this it may be concluded that complex formation is favoured in the higher pH range.

The influence of ionic strength on the absorbance values is also worth considering. It was found that the optical density values did not show any marked change in the ionic strength range of 0.15 to 0.3. When it was increased to 0.6, an appreciable change from 0.35 to 0.362 was, however, observed (Fig. 1, curves *a* and *b*), but this is possibly not the only reason for such a behaviour. The increase in optical density may be due to the increase in the amount of the complex. Harvey and Manning⁷ in their study of iron complexes of Tiron reported a similar phenomenon. Contrary to the theoretical point of view, their results showed a decrease in degree of dissociation of the complex instead of an increase at higher ionic strength.

Potentiometric titration of the complex reveals that more carboxyl groups of the acid are made available for binding with the metal as the pH of the reaction mixture is increased from 3.22 to 5.27 (studies beyond this pH could not be carried out because, unlike the complex, the metal ion was precipitated beyond pH 5.27). Such a behaviour is not unlikely in view of the high *pK* values of propionic acid (4.87). Here too, the combining ratio came out to be approximately 1:1. The value of $\log K$ was found to be 2.74 and that of $\Delta F^\circ = -3.797$ kcal.

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